

PERFORMANCE OF CERAMIC WASTE AS PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF COARSE AGGREGATE IN CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Due to the extensive use of concrete in Ethiopia during the last few decades, the demand for concrete materials has risen quickly. Due to a lack of supplies, the Ethiopian construction industry is now looking for substitute ingredients for concrete. While there is a significant need for coarse aggregate, aggregate production is having a negative impact on the environment. The purpose of this study is to see how well ceramic tile waste performs as a partial replacement for coarse aggregate in C-25, and C-30 concrete grades. The workability, unit weight, durability, and strength characteristics experiments were carried out on selected concrete grades through ceramic tile waste replaced by coarse aggregate at proportions of 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%, and the obtained results were compared to conventional concrete. The study found that replacing 20% of ceramic tile waste as an alternative of coarse aggregate reduced the unit weight of concrete and pointedly increases the compressive and tensile strength of concrete, and additionally it absorbs less water than conventional concrete. Henceforward using of Ceramic Tile waste in the concrete construction activities offers technical and environmental benefits, as well as resulting in lightweight concrete construction.

Keywords: Ceramic Tile Waste, Unit weight of concrete, Strength of concrete

1. Introduction

Over the years, generation of construction and demolition (C & D) waste has increased significantly in Ethiopia (Yehualaw and Woldesenbet, 2016). The construction and demolition waste comprised of different types of wastes arising from demolition, site clearance, land excavation, building construction etc. The construction wastes can be inert, consists of debris, soil, or non-inert construction waste, represent organic materials (Luangcharoenrat et al., 2019). The rapid economic growth and urbanization has led to extensive construction activities in the major cities of Ethiopia. The increased construction activities have known to generate large quantities of wastes causing social, environmental, and economic crisis (Kartam, N., Al-Mutairi, N., Al-Ghusain, I & Al-Humoud, J., 2004)(Kartam et al., 2018).

Aggregates are among the first construction materials that constitute major portion of civil engineering construction works. In concrete construction, aggregate constitute 60-75% by volume of which coarse aggregate is about 60-70% of total aggregate or 30-50% of the concrete volume. The demand for construction aggregate is increasing with increasing

demand of concrete as it is needed to repair existing infrastructure, create new infrastructure for the country's growing population, and to meet the demands of changing lifestyles for bigger and better houses and highways (H.Langer et al., 2005).

An attempt made on ten aggregate quarry sites of Addis Ababa, for estimating the supply demand gap in ten years shows that the demand for construction aggregate is increasing rapidly from time to time more than the existing supply with increasing demand of construction infrastructures. Also, this study revealed that aggregate production has several environmental impacts such as noise pollution, dust deposition, surface and ground water pollution, impact on the natural heritage, landscape impact and traffic impact (Semere, 2013).

Ceramic waste is one of the most active research areas that encompass a number of disciplines including civil engineering and construction materials. Ceramic waste powder is settled by sedimentation and then dumped away which results in environmental pollution, in addition to forming dust in summer and threatening both agriculture and public health. Therefore, utilization of the ceramic waste powder in various industrial sectors especially the construction, agriculture, glass and paper industries would help to protect the environment (Amitkumar D. Raval et al, 2013).

Investigations were done by different researchers on the area of solid waste management in different cities, sub-cities and towns of Ethiopia. As information from these investigations the percentage shared by Ceramic wastes and glass waste were Dessie 7.3% including metals (Solomon & Yirgalem, 2011).

2. Experimental Materials

2.1. Ceramic Tile Waste

Ceramics are made up of non-metallic compounds made permanent by a firing process which possess high hardness, high compressive strength, high elastic modulus, low thermal expansion, low density, etc. They have special advantages of lightweight; can withstand very high temperatures and aggressive environments compared to metals used mainly as coatings and sensors (Ameta et al., 2013).

Ceramic tile waste as a part of construction and demolition waste is utilized by proper reuse and replace of concrete materials in construction industry. The initial source of ceramic tile waste is collected from construction and deconstruction of structures in Hawassa city, Ethiopia. In this study, Ceramic waste was used as a partial replacement of coarse aggregate. The Primary collection of ceramic tile wastes are broken tiles with improper size. Then it is crushed by manual hammering method into required size. The crushed ceramic tile required to pass 20mm sieve and retained on 4.75mm sieve.

Table 1. Chemical properties of Ceramic Tile Waste

S. No	Materials	Ceramic Powder %
1	SiO ₂	74.14
2	Al ₂ O ₃	16.56
3	Fe ₂ O ₃	1.00
4	CaO	0.72
5	MgO	0.84
6	Na ₂ O	3.30
7	K ₂ O	2.14
8	Mn ₂ O ₃	0.04
9	P ₂ O ₅	0.07
10	TiO ₂	0.26
11	H ₂ O	0.26
12	LOI	0.43

Figure1. Collecting, crushing and Sieving of Ceramic tile Waste

Table 2. Chemical properties of Ceramic Tile Waste

S. No	Properties	Results
1	Fineness Modulus	2.54
2	Bulk Specific gravity	2.27
3	Absorption Capacity	0.67 %
4	Moisture Content	0%
5	Flakiness Index (%)	89%
6	Elongation Index (%)	41.5%
7	Soundness Value	6.10%
7	Impact Value	12.04 %

2.2. Cement

The ordinary Portland cement with class 42.5 grade being used for this research. It is conforming to European standard EN-197-1, Cement brand was Dangote brand.

2.3. Fine Aggregate

Fine aggregate is very essential ingredients in cement matrix composite which gives proper texture, improve density of Concrete produce workable concrete and act as a filler material. Dimtu sand will be used for this study, which is available in Hawassa city. Fine aggregate should be sieved in 4.75mm and retained in 150 microns sieve as per ASTM C33.

Table 3. Properties of Fine Aggregate (Sand)

S. No	Properties	Results
1	Silt Content	2.25%
2	Fineness Modulus	2.72
3	Bulk Specific gravity (SSD)	2.51
4	Water Absorption	2.04%
5	Moisture Content	1.01%

2.4. Coarse Aggregate

The segments from 30mm to 4.75 mm are used as Coarse aggregate and aggregates conforming to ASTM C33 standard. Samples were collected from Hawassa Monopole aggregate quarry site.

Table 4. Properties of Coarse Aggregate

S. No	Properties	Results
1	Fineness Modulus	3.05
2	Bulk Specific gravity (SSD)	2.58
3	Water Absorption	0.93%
4	Moisture Content	0.76%

2.5. Water

Water is an essential constituent to enhance the strength development of the concrete through hydration process. It is contributing in the chemical reaction of the concrete ingredients. For this research, clean tap water used for drinking in Hawassa University Construction Material Test Laboratory was utilized.

3. Design Mix

The study designed mix grade of C25 & C30 as per DOE (British mix design). Also, the same code was used for this study to prepare the Ceramic tile aggregate mixed concrete samples. The design and mix proportion values are shown in the table 4.

Table 5. Design Mix Proportion for C25 & C30 Mix

Mix Grade	Description	Water (Lit)	Cement (Kg)	Sand (kg)	Coarse Aggregate (kg)		
					10mm	20mm	30mm
C-25	Per 1m ³	205	310	788	220	329	494
	For 0.0822 m ³	16.851	25.482	64.774	18.084	27.044	40.607
C-30	Per 1m ³	189	350	645	251	376	565
	For 0.0715 m ³	13.514	25.025	46.118	17.946	26.884	40.398

3.1. Experimental Setup

Table 6. Waste Ceramic Percentage for Concrete

S. No	Mix Grade	Concrete Sample	CA Replacement with WCT %	Mix Grade	Concrete Sample	CA Replacement with WCT %
1	C-25	S0	0 %	C-30	S5	0 %
2		S1	10 %		S6	10 %
3		S2	20 %		S7	20 %
4		S3	30 %		S8	30 %
5		S4	40 %		S9	40 %

3.2. Mix Preparation

Experimental mix were prepared as per DoE mix design procedure for C-25 and C-30 grade of concrete made with Ceramic tile waste as replacement material of Coarse aggregate ranging from percentage 0, 10, 20, 30 and 40.

Table 7. Concrete Design Mix Proportions for C25 and C30

Mix Grade	Concrete Sample	WCT %	Cement (Kg)	Water (Lit)	CA (Kg)	WCT (Kg)	FA (Kg)	W/C Ratio
C-25	S0	0 %	25.482	16.851	85.735	0	64.774	0.63
	S1	10 %	25.482	16.851	77.162	8.574	64.774	0.63
	S2	20 %	25.482	16.851	68.588	17.147	64.774	0.63
	S3	30 %	25.482	16.851	60.015	25.720	64.774	0.63
	S4	40 %	25.482	16.851	51.441	34.294	64.774	0.63
C-30	S5	0 %	25.025	13.514	85.228	0	46.118	0.51
	S6	10 %	25.025	13.514	76.705	8.5228	46.118	0.51
	S7	20 %	25.025	13.514	68.182	17.0456	46.118	0.51
	S8	30 %	25.025	13.514	59.660	25.568	46.118	0.51
	S9	40 %	25.025	13.514	51.132	34.0912	46.118	0.51

4. Experimental Methodology

The aim of the experimental investigation is to use ceramic tile waste as a partial replacement of coarse aggregate in concrete. Experimental testing was conducted for both Fresh and hardened concrete. For hardened concrete, cube and cylinder samples were prepared and cured in water by 7days, 14 days and 28days. Then experimental results of partially replaced ceramic tile waste concrete is compared with conventional concrete.

4.1. Tests on Fresh Concrete

4.1.1. Workability Tests

The workability assessments of C-25 and C-30 concrete mixtures were assessed by placing and compacting freshly mixed concrete by rod in a mold shaped as the frustum of a cone. The mold is raised the concrete allowed to subside. The test result shows that the slump value is increased with increasing percentage of ceramic tile waste for both C-25 and C-30 concrete. This is due to less water absorption of WCT and its smooth surface properties than coarse aggregate.

Table 8. Workability Test for C25 and C30

Workability Test on Fresh concrete						
S. No	Concrete Grade	Concrete Sample	Slump Value(mm)	Concrete Grade	Concrete Sample	Slump Value(mm)
1	C25	S0	92	C30	S5	42.5
2		S1	93		S6	43.5
3		S2	95		S7	45
4		S3	98		S8	48
5		S4	103		S9	53

Figure3. Slump value for C25 & C30

4.1.2. Unit Weight Test

According to ASTM C-138 -92, Unit Weight is the determination of the weight per cubic foot or cubic meter of freshly mixed concrete. The experimental data shows that as the amount of ceramic tile replacing the coarse aggregate increased from 0% to 40% in each case for C-25 and C-30, the unit weight becomes decreased.

Table9. Unit Weight Test for C25 & C30

Unit Weight test on Fresh concrete						
S. No	Concrete Grade	Concrete Sample	Unit Weight (Kg/m ³)	Concrete Grade	Concrete Sample	Unit Weight (Kg/m ³)
1	C25	S0	2288.4	C30	S5	2323
2		S1	2271.6		S6	2295
3		S2	2258.4		S7	2293.6
4		S3	2239.6		S8	2279
5		S4	2231		S9	2259

Figure4. Unit Weight value graph for each mix

4.2. Test on hardened concrete

4.2.1. Compressive Strength of Concrete

Compression strength tests were conducted on Universal Testing machine using concrete samples. According to ASTM C 39-96 three samples were prepared from each batch, then tested and determined mean value by using MS-Excel. Then experimental test results were compared with conventional concrete with ceramic waste as 10%, 20%, 30% and 40%.

Table10. Compressive Strength test for C25 & C30

S. No	Concrete Grade	Cube Size Cm ³	Concrete Sample	WCT%	Curing period days	Compressive strength in MPa			
						Concrete samples			Mean
						1	2	3	
1	C25	15*15*15	S0	0	7	25.640	25.341	21.530	24.170
					14	28.824	26.538	27.356	27.572
					28	31.947	27.014	29.652	29.538
		15*15*15	S1	10	7	22.477	27.536	25.045	25.019
					14	30.764	28.246	28.648	29.219
					28	34.061	29.763	33.822	32.55
		15*15*15	S2	20	7	26.154	25.425	25.135	25.571
					14	32.004	28.846	27.638	29.496
					28	38.063	35.192	31.828	35.028
		15*15*15	S3	30	7	23.058	23.208	26.851	24.372
					14	27.753	25.936	27.490	27.059
					28	34.389	31.429	28.269	31.362
15*15*15	S4	40	7	21.037	21.708	18.315	20.353		
			14	23.745	23.458	21.568	22.923		
			28	25.244	25.974	23.37	24.862		
2	C30	15*15*15	S5	0	7	31.993	28.316	27.435	29.248
					14	34.493	33.178	32.986	33.552
					28	37.005	36.750	38.639	37.465
		15*15*15	S6	10	7	30.668	33.636	28.871	31.058
					14	36.284	34.926	32.116	34.442
					28	42.695	37.150	36.542	38.796
		15*15*15	S7	20	7	33.32	38.495	30.153	33.989
					14	37.753	38.786	34.428	36.989
					28	42.655	40.856	41.291	41.601
		15*15*15	S8	30	3	27.741	30.608	26.273	28.207
					14	32.265	31.974	31.543	31.927
					28	41.291	36.433	38.786	38.837
15*15*15	S9	40	7	25.008	26.046	24.468	25.174		
			14	27.650	27.984	28.417	28.017		
			28	32.434	29.420	32.994	31.616		

Figure5. Compressive Strength Value

4.2.2. Split Tensile Strength

Table11. Split tensile Strength test for C25 & C30

S. No	Concrete Grade	Cylinder Size D x L (mm)	WCT%	Curing period Days	Split tensile strength in MPa			
					Concrete samples			Mean
					1	2	3	
1	C25	150x300	0	28	3.032	2.352	2.256	2.531
			10		3.013	2.644	2.517	2.725
			20		3.067	2.656	2.666	2.796
			30		3.119	2.243	2.454	2.606
			40		2.540	2.108	2.180	2.275
2	C30		0	28	2.673	2.868	2.588	2.710
			10		3.082	2.587	3.404	3.024
			20		4.615	3.132	4.017	3.921
			30		2.927	3.437	2.881	3.082
			40		2.941	2.540	2.406	2.63

Figure6. Split tensile Strength graph

4.2.3. Water Absorption

According to ASTM C 642, after 28 days curing in water, the three cubic samples were immersed in water for 72hours in which weight measurement was took place to get constant weight. Finally, the specimen was removed from the water and surface dried to determine its saturated surface dry weight. The result was described in the following figure.

Figure7. Water Absorption test Result

4.2.4. Durability Test

Chemical attack by aggressive water is one of the factors that responsible for damage of concrete. In this case concrete samples (28days curing period) were immersed in 3.5% of sodium chloride solution for 70days to identify the attack resistance. The chloride resistance test revealed that the percentage of loss in mass of each concrete sample by comparing initial and final mass is given in the Table: 12.

Table12. Mass loss of Cubic samples after immersed in 3.5% NaCl Solution for 70 days

S. No	Concrete Sample	Size of specimen in mm ³	Initial Mass (Kg) Before Soaked in NaCl Solution	Final Mass (Kg) After immersing in NaCl Solution For 70 days	Loss in Mass (%)
1	S0	150	8.265	8.215	0.605
2	S1	150	8.875	8.825	0.563
3	S2	150	8.765	8.715	0.570
4	S3	150	8.705	8.655	0.574
5	S4	150	8.505	8.455	0.588
6	S5	150	8.765	8.715	0.570
7	S6	150	8.75	8.705	0.514
8	S7	150	8.765	8.715	0.570
9	S8	150	8.825	8.775	0.567
10	S9	150	8.755	8.705	0.571

5. Conclusion

Based on the experimental investigation with respect to the strength characteristics, the following annotations are made.

1. The findings of concrete mixing ratios C-25 and C-30 reveal that by replacing 20% of coarse aggregate with waste ceramic powder, compressive and tensile strength were increased to maximum levels, as illustrated in Tables 9 and 10.
2. Increase in replacement of waste ceramic tile with coarse aggregate reflect that decrease in concrete weight.
3. Furthermore, the analysis found that when 30% coarse aggregate is replaced with waste ceramic tile, the compression and split tensile strength is better than conventional concrete.
4. Consumption of ceramic tile wastes in construction industry are reducing environmental load and construction and demolition waste.

6. References

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